

EUROASIA

Matematik, Mühendislik, Doğa ve Tıp Bilimleri Dergisi
Journal of Mathematics, Engineering, Natural & Medical Science

Research Article

e-ISSN: 2667-6702

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20663299>

Reasons For Childhood Vaccination Refusal Among Parents Visiting Family Health Centers

Halil İbrahim ÜNSAL^{1*}, Ahmet YILMAZ²

¹ Kayapınar Parkorman Aile Sağlığı Merkezi, Diyarbakır

² Dicle Üniversitesi Aile Hekimliği Anabilim Dalı, Diyarbakır

Corresponding author E-mail: dearahmetyilmaz@hotmail.com

Article Info

Received: 10.02.2026

Accepted: 21.03.2026

Keywords

Family medicine
vaccine rejection
vaccine
prevalence
education

Abstract: Immunization is a vital primary healthcare service to prevent infants and children from infectious diseases. Identifying the reasons for vaccine rejection is a critical step in public health. This study aims to determine the perspectives and potential reasons for vaccine refusal among parents with children aged 0-14 years visiting Family Health Centers in Yenişehir, Diyarbakır. Cross-sectional descriptive study. The study was conducted with 260 parents between April and October 2019. Data were collected via a structured questionnaire covering sociodemographic characteristics and vaccine attitudes. It was found that 90.4% of participants vaccinated their children regularly. Main reasons for potential refusal included harmful substances (34.2%), perceived lack of necessity (23%), and fear of future illness (36.1%). Significant differences were observed regarding education levels and concerns about vaccine content ($p<0.001$). Vaccine refusal is a growing concern, and education is the most important measure. Coordinated training sessions in primary care are essential.

1. Introduction

Immunization is one of the most effective preventive health measures. Vaccination programs directly benefit vaccinated children, but also indirectly benefit unvaccinated individuals through herd immunity (Rashid et al., 2012). In developing countries worldwide, the World Health Organization (WHO) reports that 20% of infant deaths are due to vaccine-preventable diseases (Hacettepe Üniversitesi Nüfus Etütleri Enstitüsü, 2014). Although vaccines have achieved remarkable success, anti-vaccination attitudes still exist. This phenomenon, described as vaccine refusal, has shown an accelerating increase in our country since 2011 (Türk Tabipleri Birliği, 2018).

Vaccines contain an active ingredient, suspension liquid, preservative, and adjuvants. Because inactivated vaccines and subunit vaccines are not as immunogenic as live vaccines, they require substances called adjuvants. Adjuvant agents aim to increase the strength and duration of the immune response generated by the vaccine (Davas et al., 2018). Aluminum, used as an adjuvant, ensures the slow release of the vaccine's active ingredient and helps the immune system to mount a stronger response to the vaccine (Türkiye Enfeksiyon Hastalıkları ve Klinik Mikrobiyoloji Uzmanlık Derneği, 2016). The levels are very low, as determined by the WHO, and do not pose a risk to human health. Additionally, thiomersal continues to be used as a preservative in vaccines in many countries, and studies have found no link between thiomersal and autism (Sağlık Bakanlığı, 2024).

When examining the reasons for vaccine refusal, they generally include concerns that the chemicals in vaccines are toxic, that vaccine manufacturers may be acting maliciously, and the belief that developing natural immunity or using natural methods may be more effective in protecting against diseases (Chow et al., 2017). However, it is known that sociodemographic characteristics such as the educational level of the parents and religious beliefs also affect the vaccination frequency of children (Yiğitalp & Ertem, 2008). Insufficient and inadequate information is a major problem that hinders the effective implementation of immunization programs and leads to vaccine refusal (Argüt et al., 2016). This study aims to determine the level of knowledge about immunization among parents who consult family physicians regarding the recent increase in vaccine refusal, to re-evaluate the factors affecting vaccination practices, and to offer suggestions for reducing the rate of vaccine refusal.

2. Materials And Methods

2.1. Study Design and Population

The study received ethical approval from the Dicle University Faculty of Medicine Non-Interventional Clinical Research Ethics Committee (March 15, 2019, No: 106). This cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted in Family Health Centers located in the Yenişehir district of Diyarbakır, Turkey. The study population consisted of parents with infants or children aged 0-14 years who visited the centers between April 15, 2019, and October 15, 2019. The minimum required sample size was determined to be 260 participants using sample size calculation software (The Survey System, <http://www.surveysystem.com/sscalc.htm>) with a 95% confidence level.

2.2. Data Collection

Data were collected using a 15-item structured questionnaire developed by the researchers based on a comprehensive literature review. The questionnaire gathered information on the sociodemographic characteristics of the families (e.g., gender and age of both the child and the interviewed parent, parental education, and employment status). It also assessed variables related to vaccination practices, including regular vaccination status, knowledge about school-age and required vaccinations, decision-makers regarding vaccination, sources of vaccine information, reasons for vaccine refusal, and the parents' demand for comprehensive educational seminars. Following the acquisition of verbal and written informed consent, data were collected through face-to-face interviews with the voluntary participants.

2.3. Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 24.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Descriptive statistics for continuous variables were presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) and median (minimum–maximum values). Categorical variables were expressed as frequencies (n) and percentages (%). The chi-square test was employed to analyze the relationships

between categorical variables. A p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant, while $p < 0.001$ was considered highly statistically significant.

3. Results

The study included 260 patients, 134 of whom (51.5%) were male. The sociodemographic characteristics of the patients participating in the study are detailed in Table 1.

Table 1. Sociodemographic characteristics of the participants

Feature	n	%
Baby/Child Gender		
Male	134	51.5
Female	126	48.5
Interviewed parent		
Mother	153	58.8
Father	107	41.2
Parental education level		
Illiterate	25	9.6
Primary/Middle School	78	30.0
High school	44	16.9
University	113	43.5

Our study found that 90.4% of participants regularly vaccinated their babies/children, 86.9% were knowledgeable about school-age vaccinations, and 90% believed that vaccination was necessary. Participants' attitudes towards vaccination and vaccine knowledge are detailed in Table 2.

Table 2. Participants' attitudes towards vaccination and vaccine knowledge

Features	n	%
Getting vaccinations done regularly		
Getting it done	235	90.4
Doesn't do it regularly	25	9.6
Informed about school-age vaccinations		
I have information	226	86.9
I don't know	34	13.1
Is vaccination necessary?		
Necessary	234	90.0
Unnecessary	26	10.0

When participants were asked about their sources of information regarding vaccines, it was found that 77.7% of them cited midwives/nurses/doctors, i.e., healthcare professionals, as their primary source of information. 47% of participants stated that parents influenced their decision regarding vaccination.

Table 3. Possible reasons for vaccine refusal

Features	n	%
Factors influencing the decision		
Mother and Father	122	47.0
Family elders / Circle of friends	65	25.0
Media / Press organizations	73	28.0
Possible reasons for refusal		
Belief that ingredients are harmful	89	34.2
Vaccine is unnecessary	60	23.0
Vaccine is for commercial purposes	17	6.5
Fear of future illnesses	94	36.1
Information sources about vaccines		
Midwife/Nurse/Doctor	202	77.7
Friends/Neighbors	24	9.2
Media, Press and Broadcasting	34	13.1

When comparing the reasons for vaccine refusal between those with an education level above high school and those below high school, significant differences were observed regarding the belief that vaccines contain harmful substances and are commercially driven ($p < 0.001$).

Table 4. Evaluating the reasons for vaccine refusal according to education level

Features	Below high school	High school and above	p
Getting vaccinated regularly (yes)	92 (39.1%)	143 (60.9%)	0.637
Contains harmful substances (yes)	39 (37.9%)	95 (60.5%)	<0.001
Vaccines are useless (yes)	36 (35.0%)	62 (39.5%)	0.460
The vaccine is commercial (yes)	7 (6.8%)	59 (37.6%)	<0.001
Source: Media (yes)	17 (16.5%)	85 (54.1%)	<0.001

The study found that participants who used media as a source and perceived vaccines as commercial were mostly in the 26-34 age group ($p < 0.05$).

Table 5. Evaluating the reasons for vaccine refusal according to age group

Features	18-25	26-34	≥35	p
The vaccine is commercial (yes)	1 (2.9%)	46 (34.1%)	19 (21.1%)	<0.001
Source: Media (yes)	5 (14.3%)	63 (46.7%)	37 (37.8%)	0.002

4. Discussion

Immunization is a low-risk and effective public health method for preventing infectious diseases (Tensak, 2010). The literature reports that parental education, residence, and socioeconomic status are major factors influencing vaccination (Argüt et al., 2016; Gülgün et al., 2014; Yiğitalp & Ertem, 2008). In a study by Özkan et al., 54% of parents were primary school graduates (Özkan & Çatiker, 2006). Conversely, our study found no significant correlation between regular vaccination and parents' education level or employment status. This may be due to the high level of trust in healthcare professionals in our study region.

Regarding refusal reasons, Khaliq et al. reported that 21.3% of parents in Karachi were concerned about side effects (Khaliq et al., 2017). Similarly, a 2017 study in Austria found that 35.9% of parents feared side effects and 23.1% believed vaccines were commercially driven (Sandhofer et al., 2017). A study in India identified lack of information as a primary cause (52.4%) (Kumar et al., 2010). Our research identified similar concerns, showing that parents fear potential future harm to their children.

The influence of media is also prominent. Studies in America show that 55% of individuals obtain health info online, where 43% of top search results are anti-vaccine websites (Davies et al., 2002; Kata, 2010). Our research found that 13.1% of parents use media as a source, which significantly impacts those with existing doubts. While literature from Ankara (97.5%) and other regions shows a high reliance on healthcare professionals (Derince, 2006; Kürtüncü et al., 2017; Taşar & Dallar, 2015), our study confirms that midwives, nurses, and doctors remain the most trusted information sources (77.7%). Finally, 98% of parents expressed a need for further education on vaccines, highlighting a demand for reliable information.

5. Conclusion

Vaccination rates are high, but trust issues exist regarding vaccine content, particularly among educated parents aged 26-34 who use social media. Authorities must focus on multidisciplinary education and effective media use to maintain public trust.

Ethical Approval

Ethical approval was obtained from Dicle University Faculty of Medicine Non-Interventional Clinical Research Ethics Committee (March 15, 2019, No: 106).

Author Contributions

All authors have contributed equally.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this article.

Funding

Not funding

References

- Argüt N, Yetim A, Gökçay G. (2016). Factors influencing vaccine acceptance. *Children's Magazine (In English)*. 16(1):16-24.
- Chow MY, Danchin M, Willaby HW, Pemberton S, Leask J. (2017). Parental attitudes, beliefs, behaviours and concerns towards childhood vaccinations in Australia: A national online survey. *Aust Fam Physician*. 46(3):145-51.
- Davas A, Özyurt B, İrgil E, Etiler N, Yasin Y. (2018). General information about immunization (In English). In: Etiler N, editor. *Vaccination guidelines for primary healthcare workers (In English)*. Ankara: Turkish Medical Association Publications (In English); p. 11-39.
- Davies P, Chapman S, Leask J. (2002). Antivaccination activists on the world wide web. *Arch Dis Child*. 87(1):22-5.
- Derince D. (2006). Evaluation of knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors regarding immunization among mothers with children aged 0-59 months at İnönü Central Health Center in Eskişehir Province (In English). [Master's thesis]. Afyonkarahisar: Afyon Kocatepe University Institute of Health Sciences (In English).
- Gülgün M, Fidancı K, Karaoğlu A, Güneş Ö, Kesik V, Altun S, et al. (2014). Evaluation of vaccination status of children aged 0-24 months who presented to the pediatric outpatient clinic of a military hospital (In English). *Gulhane Med J*. 56:13-6.
- Hacettepe University Institute of Population Studies. (2014). *Turkey Population and Health Survey 2013*. Ankara: Hacettepe University (In English).
- Kata A. (2010). A postmodern Pandora's Box: Anti-vaccination misinformation on the internet. *Vaccine*. 28(7):1709-16.
- Khaliq A, Sayed SA, Hussaini SA, Azam K, Qamar M. (2017). Missed immunization opportunities among children under 5 years of age dwelling in Karachi city. *J Ayub Med Coll Abbottabad*. 29(4):645-9.

- Kumar D, Aggarwal A, Gomber S. (2010). Immunization status of children admitted to a tertiary-care hospital of North India: reasons for partial immunization or non-immunization. *J Health Popul Nutr.* 28(3):300-4.
- Kürtüncü M, Alkan I, Bahadır Ö, Arslan N. (2017). The level of knowledge of mothers regarding the vaccination status of their children living in rural areas of Zonguldak (In English). *Electron J Vocat Coll.* 7(Special Issue):8-17.
- Özkan Ö, Çatiker A. (2006). Vaccination status and disabilities of children in Bolu city center (In English) *STED.* 15(10):171-7.
- Rashid H, Khandaker G, Booy R. (2012). Vaccination and herd immunity. *Curr Opin Infect Dis.* 25(3):243-9.
- Sandhofer MJ, Robak O, Frank H, Kulning J. (2017). Vaccine hesitancy in Austria: A cross-sectional survey. *Wien Klin Wochenschr.* 129(1-2):59-64.
- Ministry of Health. (2024). Vaccine contents [Internet]. Ankara: Republic of Turkey Ministry of Health.(In English); [cited 27 Apr 2024].
- Taşar MA, Daller YB. (2015). Examining missed vaccination opportunities in a socioeconomically disadvantaged area of Ankara (In English). *TAF Prev Med Bull.* 14(4):279-83.
- Tensak D. (2010). Immunization status of children and factors affecting it in a primary care area (In English) [Master's thesis]. Mersin: Mersin University Institute of Health Sciences (In English).
- Turkish Medical Association (TTB). (2018). Ethics committee opinion on vaccine hesitancy, vaccine refusal and anti-vaccination sentiment [Internet]. Ankara: TTB (In English).
- Turkish Society of Infectious Diseases and Clinical Microbiology. (2016). Adult immunization guide. Istanbul: Arvin Publishing House (In English).
- Yiğitalp G, Ertem M. (2008). Reasons for absenteeism from vaccinations for children aged 0-12 months in Diyarbakır province (In English). *TAF Prev Med Bull.* 7(4):277-84.